

Analysis of the State educational standard in mathematics in primary grades

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Annotatsiya: Talabalarga boshlang'ich sinflar matematika ta'limi mazmuni, tuzilishi xususiyatlariga oid ko'nikma va malakalarini mustahkamlash, boshlang'ich sinflar uchun matematikadan Davlat ta'lim standarti (2017 yil tasdiqlangan)ni puxta o'zlashtirishni ta'minlash.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat ta'lim standarti, fan, o'quv dasturi, darslik, metod, metodika, o'rgatish, o'qitish, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, predmet, maqsad, vazifa, fanlararo bog'liqlik. Dars materiallari: D.T.S

Аннотация: Закрепить умения и навыки учащихся, связанные с содержанием и структурой обучения математике в начальной школе, обеспечить углубленное освоение ГОСО по математике в начальной школе (утвержден в 2017 году).

Ключевые слова: государственный образовательный стандарт, наука, учебная программа, учебник, метод, методика, обучение, обучение, знание, умение, компетенция, предмет, цель, задача, междисциплинарность. Материалы урока: Д.Т.С.

Annotation: To strengthen students' skills and abilities related to the content and structure of elementary school mathematics education, to ensure thorough mastering of the State Educational Standard for elementary school mathematics (approved in 2017).

Key words: state educational standard, science, curriculum, textbook, method,

methodology, teaching, teaching, knowledge, skill, competence, subject, goal, task, interdisciplinarity . Lesson materials: D.T.S

The state educational standard of general secondary education determines the goals and objectives, main principles, components of the state educational standard, the procedure for introducing state educational standards and monitoring compliance with the requirements of the state educational standards. The development of the state education standard is based on the following documents: Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education"; Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the National Personnel Training Program"; Resolution No. 5 of January 5, 1998 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development and practical implementation of state education standards for the continuing education system"; Resolution No. 124 dated May 8, 2013 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the state education standard for foreign languages of the continuing education system"; Resolution No. 140 of March 15, 2017 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the regulation on general secondary education"; UzDSt 1.0-98. "State standardization system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Basic rules"; UzDSt 1.1-92. "State standardization system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Procedures for development, coordination, approval and registration of standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan"; Own DSt 1.5-93. "Procedure for reviewing, checking, amending and revoking normative documents on standardization"; Own DSt 1157:2008. Document unification system. System of organizational documents. Requirements for formalization of documents. Own DSt 1.8:2009. Basic rules. Recommendations. Fulfillment of the state educational standard is mandatory for all general secondary educational institutions operating in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The word "standard" is English and means "copy", "size", "standard". Concepts of standard, standards of

standardization, DTS defines the forms, tools, methods of educational content and the procedure for evaluating their quality. It is necessary to ensure a stable level of education in various educational institutions (state and non-state) operating in the territory of the country by means of the standard, which is the core of the educational content. DTS, in its essence, serves as a basis for creating educational programs, textbooks, training manuals, regulations, curriculum and other normative documents. Fulfilling the DTS and its requirements is mandatory for all educational institutions operating in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of the form of ownership and departmental subordination. As a component of DTS, a basic curriculum for general secondary (vocational and higher) educational institutions will be developed. The basic curriculum is considered a state document, which is the basis for the regulation of educational fields and the basis for ensuring the financial support of educational institutions. The basic curriculum determines the minimum amount of study hours allocated to deliver the content of education to the learner.

The introduction of state educational standards implies the following goals:

- to ensure the high quality of education and the deep economic and social reforms implemented in the country, training of competitive personnel that meets the requirements of building a developed democratic state;
- regulating the content of personnel training based on the prospects of social and economic development of the country, the needs of society, modern achievements of science, technology and technology;
- democratization, humanization and socialization of education, increasing the level of legal and economic knowledge of educators, as well as the effectiveness of the educational process;
- providing quality educational services, protecting the interests of the individual, society and the state in the field of education and personnel training;

- determining the criteria and procedure for evaluating the quality of personnel training and educational activity;
- ensuring consistency and continuity of the educational process and personnel training;
- ensuring competitiveness in the market of labor and educational services. Tasks of state educational standards:
 - determination of acceptable requirements for the quality of education and personnel training, the types of educational services provided;
 - to create a normative basis that defines the relevant requirements for education and its final results, the procedure for periodically assessing the level of knowledge and professional qualifications of learners, as well as for monitoring the quality of educational activities;
 - introduction of effective forms and methods of spiritual and moral education of students based on the rich intellectual heritage of the nation and universal human values;
 - in all types of education, to agree on their content and education and upbringing, to ensure their interdependence, consistency in the continuous education system and personnel training;
 - setting standards and requirements for the education and training process, providing pedagogical and information technologies, monitoring the level of education, qualifications of students and graduates in educational institutions;
 - introduction of an impartial system of assessment of the quality of education and personnel training, attestation and accreditation of educational institutions;
 - ensuring the effective integration of education, science and production for purposeful and high-quality training of personnel;
 - to ensure compliance with international requirements regarding the quality of education and training of personnel in accordance with national standards.

The purpose of the state education standard is to organize the general secondary education system based on the socio-economic reforms implemented in the country, best practices of developed foreign countries and science and modern information and communication technologies. consists in educating a developed personality. The tasks of the state educational standard are as follows: setting requirements for the content and quality of general secondary education; introduction of effective forms and methods of educating students based on national, universal and spiritual values; introduction of pedagogical and modern information and communication technologies into the educational process, setting requirements for the qualifications of students and graduates of general secondary educational institutions; ensuring effective integration of education, science and production for purposeful and high-quality training of personnel; improvement of the procedure for systematic assessment of education and its final results, the level of students' achievement of qualification requirements, as well as the legal basis for monitoring the quality of educational activities; to ensure compliance of the requirements of the state educational standards with the international requirements for the quality of education and personnel training.

The state education standard is based on the following main principles: the priority of the student's personality, his aspirations, abilities and interests; humanitarian content of general secondary education; compliance of the state education standard with the requirements of the state and society in the field of education, and the needs of the individual; continuity of general secondary education with other types and stages of education and coherence of educational content; unity and integrity of general secondary education content in all regions of the republic; that the content, form, means and methods of general secondary education are based on innovative technologies; provision of support for students to learn subjects and to continue their education and development of general competences related to

subjects; using the experience of setting standards in the field of education of developed foreign countries, taking into account national characteristics.

Course of training:

In the practical session, in order to activate the students, the following questions will be answered so that they can consciously master today's topic:

1. What is the state education standard?
2. What is its structure?
3. What is the purpose of the state educational standard?
4. What are the tasks of the state education standard?
5. Tell the main principles of the state education standard?
6. D.T.S. What and in what year is it reflected in the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers?
7. Who makes the curriculum? And when was the last one accepted?
8. How many hours are allocated in the curriculum for 1st grade mathematics lessons?
9. How many hours are allocated in the curriculum for 2nd grade mathematics lessons?
10. How did you understand the basic curriculum?
How many sections does the curriculum for 11.1 grade mathematics classes consist of?
12. How many sections are divided in the curriculum for 2nd grade mathematics classes?
13. Tell the names of the sections allocated for the 1st grade mathematics lessons in sequence.
14. Tell the names of the departments allocated for the 2nd grade mathematics lessons in sequence.
15. Explain the difference between the structure of mathematics lessons for 1st

grade and 2nd grade based on the comparison of the curriculum?

Students are divided into two groups and assigned to groups:

Group 1 1. Describe and explain the elements of subject competence formed in the students of the 1st grade?

2. Explain the elements of subject competence formed by 3rd graders? 2. Prepare for the presentation as a team?

Note: 1) time to complete the work - 15 minutes Group 2 1. Describe and explain the elements of competence related to science formed by students of the 2nd grade? Homework: D.T.S. and analysis of curriculum and primary school textbooks.

Summary

In conclusion, we can say that the goal of the state education standard is to organize the general secondary education system based on the socio-economic reforms implemented in the country, best practices of developed foreign countries, and science and modern information and communication technologies. is to educate a spiritually mature and intellectually developed person.

References:

1. Jumayev M.E. Methodology of teaching mathematics (textbook for OO'Y) Tashkent. "Turon-Iqbal" 2016 p. 426.
2. Jumayev M.E, Tadjiyeva Z.G'. Methodology of teaching mathematics in primary grades. (Textbook for OO'Y.) Tashkent. "Science and Technology" 2005.
3. Jumayev M.E., Practicum on the methodology of teaching mathematics in

primary grades. (for OO'Y) Tashkent. "Teacher" 2004.